

THE EFFECT OF FIBRE-BUNDLING ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF A SHORT-FIBRE COMPOSITE

David R. Mulligan¹, Stephen L. Ogin¹, Paul A. Smith¹,
Garry M. Wells² and Christopher M. Worrall²

¹*Department of Materials Science and Engineering,
University of Surrey, Guildford, Surrey, GU2 5XH, UK*

²*Kobe Steel Europe Ltd. Research Laboratory,
10 Nugent Rd., Surrey Research Park, Guildford, Surrey GU2 5AF, UK.*

SUMMARY : The effect of fibre-bundling on the tensile modulus and tensile strength of short carbon fibre reinforced polypropylene composite materials has been investigated. The fibre was either filamentised or in bundles of 6000 fibres. Materials containing 0 %, 25 %, 50 %, 75 % and 100 % of the fibres in bundles were produced. It was found that fibre-bundling leads to a significant reduction in both the tensile modulus and tensile strength compared with the fully filamentised composite. The reduced reinforcing efficiency of fibre bundles compared to individual fibres has been estimated using the Cox model. This approach gives reasonable agreement with the experimental modulus of laminates containing only filamentised fibres or only fibre bundles, but overestimates the modulus of laminates containing a mixture of fibres and bundles.

KEYWORDS : fibre-bundling, mesostructure, short-fibre composite

INTRODUCTION

The longitudinal Young's modulus of a continuous aligned composite material can be predicted satisfactorily from the constituent moduli and the fibre volume fraction using a simple rule-of-mixtures expression. Such an expression may be modified for a short-fibre composite by introducing factors which account for the reduced reinforcing efficiency of short-fibres [1] and the orientation of the fibres [2]. In calculating the reduced reinforcing efficiency, it is usually assumed that individual fibres are the basic unit of reinforcement and that they are straight, aligned and regularly spaced. However it is generally the case that at least some of the fibres are in clusters, or even bundles, reflecting the tow structure from which they were cut originally. The behaviour of fibres contained in bundles will differ from that of an equivalent number of fibres dispersed more uniformly. This type of structure, on a scale between that of the individual fibre and that of the material as a whole, has been described as mesostructure [3], and is not usually a feature of models for composite materials.

A number of workers have studied the effect of fibre-bundling, with the objective of improving the toughness of composite materials. The most frequently used method to manufacture a composite with the fibres in bundles is to impregnate a fibre tow with a resin, which is then cured, and the resulting rod is subsequently manufactured into a laminate. The first study to use this technique was by Fila, Bredin and Piggott [4] who constructed continuous, aligned laminates of glass or carbon fibre in a copolymer of styrene and polyester. A similar approach was taken

by Kim and Mai [5] who manufactured random and aligned discontinuous fibre composites of carbon fibre bundles impregnated with epoxy resin or polycarbonate, in an epoxy resin matrix. Both of these studies recommended this as a method to achieve tougher composite materials. While this approach has yielded some valuable results there are obvious difficulties if the aim is to examine the mechanisms associated with fibre bundling, the most significant being the extra interface that is created between the polymer used to impregnate the bundle and the polymer matrix.

Ericson and Berglund [6] compared two types of glass-mat-reinforced polypropylene; these contained either short individual fibres or looped (continuous) fibre bundles. They found that the material containing individual short-fibres had a higher modulus and a slightly higher strength. They accounted for the reduced modulus of the bundled material in terms of the reduced reinforcing efficiency of the bundles, which was estimated using the Cox model applied to the bundles. This work is important since it considers commercially manufactured materials and ultimately the findings of this area of work should be used to produce composite materials which achieve the required properties in the most efficient manner.

There is a limited amount of theoretical work on fibre-bundling. The most relevant treatment is by Kataoka, Taya and Saito [7], who analysed the case of a composite material containing fibres and fibre clusters, using the Eshelby method. They found that with regard to the Young's modulus the most significant variable was the volume fraction of bundles in the material. The fibre volume fraction in the bundle, the fibre aspect ratio and bundle aspect ratio all had relatively minor effects on the Young's modulus. Trapeznikov, Toropov, and Loskutov[8] modelled the effect of fibre-bundling on the strength of a carbon-carbon composite and found that the strength of the material decreased when the number of fibres in the tow forming the bundle was increased.

Methods for quantifying the degree of fibre-bundling in a random short-fibre composite are currently under development. For example Worrall and Wells [9] have described a "fractal-variance characterisation method", which they used successfully to analyse the size of bundles in a material. However it is not possible, at present, to find the volume fraction of bundles of a given size using this technique.

The present work is aimed at characterising the effect of fibre-bundling on the mechanical properties of a carefully controlled range of short-fibre composite materials in which the volume fraction of the fibre in bundles has been varied. The mass of the individual fibre mats used to produce the composites varied, resulting in differences in the overall volume fraction and a normalisation procedure has been carried out to enable the results to be compared. Data are presented for the moduli and strength of the materials.

EXPERIMENTAL

The carbon fibre tow (Torayca T300), consisting of 6000 fibres, was coated with molten wax, which solidified before the tow was chopped into 5 mm lengths by a chopping machine. The fibre could be incorporated in the mats in this form, resulting in bundles in the mat, or the wax could be burnt off, resulting in filamentised fibres in the mat. The appropriate proportions of wax-coated and uncoated fibre were dispersed in a glycerine solution and the mixture was poured over a stainless steel mesh to produce a random mat. The mats were washed and then dried at 100 °C, and the wax was burnt off the wax-coated bundles in the mat to produce mats which had varying proportions of bundled and filamentised fibres. Mats with the following compositions

were produced; 0 % bundles (i.e completely filamentised), 25 % bundles, 50 % bundles, 75 % bundles and 100 % bundles

The mats were impregnated with the polypropylene matrix using a film stacking technique. Layers of carbon fibre were interleaved with polypropylene film to give a laminate approximately 1 mm thick and an overall volume fraction of about 0.15. This stack was heated to 250 °C for three minutes with contact pressure, then full pressure was applied for one minute. During this time the pressure was released three times to "pump" the stack, which allowed entrapped air to escape and aided the infiltration of the fibre bundles by the polymer melt. To verify that infiltration was satisfactory, samples from the laminates were mounted in epoxy resin and sectioned using a Jung microtome with a glass knife. Sections 20 µm thick were viewed in transmission on an Axiophot microscope and showed no evidence of porosity.

Tensile test coupons, 150 mm long by 20 mm wide, were cut from the composite plates using a water-lubricated diamond saw. The coupons were tensile tested on an Instron 1175 with 30 mm long friction tabs made from emery cloth. A crosshead speed of 0.5 mm / min was used and the strain on the sample was measured using a 50 mm gauge length extensometer, which was attached to the specimen surface with rubber bands. Five specimens were tested for each laminate type.

The volume fraction of the laminates was found using a burn-off method. From each laminate four samples of about 0.5 g were accurately weighed and then heated to 420 °C in a crucible for five hours. After cooling, the mass of the residue was determined. The volume fractions were calculated based on density values of 1.76 g/cm³ for the carbon fibre and 0.90 g/cm³ for the polypropylene.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Tensile Modulus

The tensile modulus was calculated by applying a linear regression fit to the stress-strain curve between 0 % and 0.5 % strain. The results are shown in Fig. 1 and the values for the overall fibre volume fractions are indicated. The results show a large reduction in the modulus of the laminates with an increase in the percentage of fibres in bundles. Previous work by Ericson and Berglund [6] accounted for a lower than expected modulus for a bundled material by considering the bundle as a large fibre and calculating the length efficiency factor accordingly. In the present study such an approach is developed to allow for the presence of filamentised fibres in the matrix surrounding the bundle.

The usual expression for a randomly oriented short fibre composite is :

$$E_c = \eta_o \eta_l E_f V_f + E_m V_m \quad (1)$$

where E_c , E_f and E_m are the modulus of the composite, fibre and matrix respectively; η_o is the Krenchel orientation factor [2], which is taken as 0.375 for a planar random fibre architecture; η_l is the length efficiency factor; V_f and V_m are the volume fractions of fibre and matrix respectively.

Fig. 1: Graph showing the variation of tensile modulus with percentage of fibres in bundles (the data points are labelled with the volume fraction of the laminate)

Eqn 1 may be modified to include a third term that represents the contribution of the fibre bundles i.e.

$$E_c = \eta_o \eta_{lo} E_f V_{fo} + \eta_o \eta_{lb} E_b (V_{fb} + V_{mb}) + E_m V_{mo} \quad (2)$$

In this modified expression V_{fo} , V_{fb} , V_{mo} and V_{mb} are volume fractions, where the first subscript, “f” or “m”, describes whether the volume fraction is of fibre or matrix, while the second subscript, “b” or “o”, indicates whether a component is inside a fibre bundle, “b”, or outside a fibre bundle, “o”. These definitions result in :

$$V_f = V_{fo} + V_{fb} \quad (3)$$

$$V_m = V_{mo} + V_{mb} \quad (4)$$

Table 1 shows the value of these quantities for composites with an overall fibre volume fraction (V_f) of 0.15 and a volume fraction of fibres in the bundled region of 0.6 i.e.

$$V_{fb} / (V_{fb} + V_{mb}) = 0.6 \quad (5)$$

Table 1 : The values of the four volume fraction terms for the laminates

<i>laminates/ % bundles</i>	V_f	V_{fb}	V_{fb}	V_m	V_{mb}	V_{mb}
0	0.150	0.150	0.000	0.850	0.850	0.000
25	0.150	0.113	0.038	0.850	0.825	0.025
50	0.150	0.075	0.750	0.850	0.800	0.050
75	0.150	0.038	0.113	0.850	0.775	0.075
100	0.150	0.000	0.150	0.850	0.750	0.100

E_b , the modulus of the bundle, is calculated using the Voigt model for a continuous aligned composite applied to the fibre bundle:

$$E_b = E_f V_{fb} + E_m V_{mb} \quad (6)$$

Table 2 shows the values of the three moduli, together with other values used in the calculation.

Table 2 : Values used in the modulus calculation

Tensile modulus of fibre	E_f	230 GPa
Tensile modulus of bundle	E_b	139 GPa
Tensile modulus of matrix	E_m	1.40 GPa
Shear modulus of matrix	G_m	0.54 GPa
Radius of fibre	r (for η_{fb})	3.95×10^{-6} m
Radius of bundle	r (for η_{fb})	3.95×10^{-4} m

The length efficiency factors in Eqn 2 account for the reduced reinforcing efficiency of a discontinuous reinforcement compared to continuous reinforcement and were calculated using the expressions from Cox[1] i.e.

$$\eta_l = 1 - \frac{\tanh(\beta l/2)}{(\beta l/2)} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\beta = \sqrt{\frac{2 G_m}{E_f r^2 \ln(R/r)}} \quad (8)$$

The length efficiency factor for the filamentised fibres (η_{fb}) is derived by considering only the material outside the fibre bundles. The length efficiency factor for the filamentised fibres (η_{fb}) is calculated by considering the bundles as reinforcing fibres within a “matrix” that consists of polypropylene and filamentised fibres. The resulting values of the efficiency factors are shown in table 3.

Table 3 : The resulting values of η_{fb} and η_{fb} .

<i>Laminate</i>	η_{fb}	η_{fb}
0% bundles	0.978	-
25% bundles	0.976	0.352
50% bundles	0.974	0.351
75% bundles	0.971	0.297
100% bundles	-	0.127

Based on the steps outlined above the moduli of the composites can be calculated from Eqn 2. Further, it is possible to normalise the experimental results for the fibre volume fraction, using the relation shown in Eqn 9.

$$\text{Normalised experimental modulus} = \frac{\text{Prediction for } V_f = 0.15}{\text{Prediction for actual } V_f} \times \text{experimental value} \quad (9)$$

The normalised experimental results and the predictions from the model are shown in Fig. 2, based on a fibre volume fraction of 0.15. A comparison of the two curves in Fig. 2 shows that while there is good agreement for the 0% and 100% materials, the model overestimates significantly the modulus of the laminates when there is a mixture of fibres and bundles present. It seems that this is because the presence of fibre bundles reduces the efficiency of the filamentised fibres; it is unlikely that the filamentised fibres are distributed evenly in the presence of bundles. In particular it seems likely that there will be matrix-rich regions in the vicinity of the bundles and these may contribute to the observed moduli.

Fig. 2 : Graph showing the tensile modulus predictions from the modified Cox model and the normalised experimental data.

Tensile Strength

The values for the tensile strength were taken from the maximum stress on the stress-strain curve. The results are shown in Fig. 3. The results show that the strength for the 25% to 100% materials is reasonably constant and about a quarter of the strength of the filamentised material.

This suggests that the reduction in strength is due to the presence of bundles, rather than the volume fraction of bundles. It seems reasonable to suggest that the failure is initiated either at bundles oriented transverse to the applied stress, or at bundle ends when they are aligned with the tensile load. The same sites are likely to be preferred for the propagation of the crack, although in this case the transversely oriented bundles are likely to be more significant. This interpretation supports the shape of the graph in Fig. 3, since even in the 25% bundle material there will be regions where there are a number of bundles spaced closely together.

Fig. 3 : Graph showing the variation of tensile strength with percentage of fibres in bundles

CONCLUSIONS

Fibre-bundling was found to have a substantial effect on both the tensile modulus and tensile strength of a short-fibre composite. An analysis using the Cox model gives reasonable agreement for both the filamentised and the completely bundled material, but overestimates the moduli of the materials containing a mixture of fibres and bundles. The tensile strength data show that the strength of laminates containing 25% to 100% of the fibres within bundles is about one quarter of the strength of a filamentised material.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank Mr. R. Whittingham of the University of Surrey for his help with the manufacture of fibre mats, Mr. P. Ives of Kobe Steel Europe Ltd. for his invaluable assistance with the film-stacking technique and Kobe Steel Europe Ltd. and the EPSRC for funding a CASE studentship for D. Mulligan

REFERENCES

1. Cox, H. L., "The elasticity and strength of paper and other fibrous materials", *British Journal of Applied Physics*, Vol. 3, 1952, pp. 72-75.
2. Krenchel, H., "Fibre Reinforcement", Akademisk Forlag, Copenhagen, 1964.
3. Piggott, M. R., "Preface: Realistic models for fibre composites", *Composites Science & Technology*, Vol. 53, 1995, pp. 121-122.
4. Fila, M., Bredin, C. and Piggott, M., "Work of fracture of fibre-reinforced polymers", *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 7, 1972, pp. 983-988.
5. Kim, J. K. and Mai, Y. W., "Fracture of CFRP containing impregnated fibre bundles", *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 49, 1993, pp. 51-60.
6. Ericson, M. and Berglund, L., "Deformation and fracture of glass-mat-reinforced polypropylene", *Composites Science & Technology*, Vol. 43, 1992, pp. 269-281.
7. Kataoka, Y., Taya, M. and Saito, M., "Effect of fibre clustering on the stiffness and strength of a short fibre composite", *Proceedings of the seventh Japan/U.S. Conference on Composite Materials*, Kyoto, Japan, June 19-22 1995, Ch. 93, pp. 505-514.
8. Trapeznikov, D. A., Toropov, A. I., and Loskutov, O. D., "Modelling approach to optimization of mechanical properties of discontinuous fibre-reinforced C/C composites", *Composites*, Vol. 23, No. 3, 1992, pp. 174-182.
9. Worrall, C. M. and Wells, G. M., "Fibre distribution in discontinuous fibre reinforced plastics: Characterisation and effect on material performance", *Proceedings of the seventh European Conference on Composite Materials*, London, U. K., May 14-16 1996, Vol. 1. pp. 247-252.